

ENVRI-FAIR

ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building Fair services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research

Project Information

URL: www.envri-fair.eu

Project Coordinator: Forschungszentrum Juelich

Coordinator Country: Germany

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Project mission

The overarching goal of ENVRI-FAIR is to implement FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable) principles in the ENVRI (European Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures) community and connect it to the European Open Science Cloud. ENVRI-FAIR targets the development and implementation of both technical frameworks and policy solutions that make subdomain boundaries irrelevant for environmental scientists and prepare Earth system science for the new Open Science paradigm and truly interdisciplinary science.

Type of synergy

Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud: As part of ENVRI-FAIR Blue-Cloud has reviewed the FAIRness of data discovery and access services of multiple RIs, divided over 4 domains (marine, atmosphere, terrestrial, life) and analysed how each of the RIs could improve their FAIRness considering services and formats. These improvements are being made, whereby they work together per domain, but also have horizontal exchanges so that domains and RIS can learn from each other and can adopt and adapt common solutions.

To try out and demonstrate the progress in FAIRness, ENVRI-FAIR has also deployed domain Use Cases, like the Marine Data Demonstrator which has a focus on the Marine RIs in ENVRI-FAIR and selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOV's). Moreover, work has been ongoing on the ENVRI Knowledge Base which documents best practices, solutions, etc in the different domains for improving FAIRness. And finally there is work ongoing on a ENVRI Catalogue which will describe in metadata the various services of the RIs in ENVRI-FAIR.

These 3 components together, Use Cases - Knowledge Base - Catalogue, are the ENVRI-HUB, which has a prototype character and can be seen as a proof-of-concept to demonstrate the outcome of the ENVRI-FAIR activities. It is fully focused on metadata.

Sustainable results of ENVRI-FAIR are the improved and upgraded services at each of the RIs and their increased mutual coherence as well as the methodologies and documentation applied in ENVRI-FAIR for achieving these results.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: ENVRI-FAIR supports the development of the Blue-Cloud roadmap from a strategic point of view, providing insights into the EU Digital Twin Ocean. Moreover, several marine partners and Blue Data Infrastructures from Blue-Cloud participated in the ENVRI-FAIR FAIRness exercise and the marine EOV demonstrator. The resulting insights and improvements have positively contributed to the design and development of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud has joined the ENVRI Week in Dresden on 3-7 February 2020 in a poster session focussed on highlighting the main goals of the project. [Andreas Petzold](#), ENVRI-FAIR Project coordinator, joined the Round Table “*Building and bringing a thriving marine Open Science community into EOSC: Opportunities & outstanding challenges*” at the [Blue-Cloud Final event](#) in Brussels, on the 8th of December 2022.